

According to [firsthow.com](https://www.firsthow.com) "COVID-19 is a member of the SARS-CoV-2 family. People who have underlying medical conditions like heart or lung disease might be at higher risk for developing more serious complications from COVID-19." This deadly virus spreads from person to person by talking, coughing, or sneezing an infected person.

Key Facts

[Firsthow](https://www.firsthow.com) has described in detail covid-19 disease and facts about covid-19. Here we are going to define the basic key facts of covid-19

- COVID-19 virus spreads through respiratory droplets by an infected person's coughs, sneezes, or even talks.
- Symptoms appear between 2-14 days after someone is infected by this virus and can include fever, chills, and cough.
- Some people who are infected may not have symptoms because of a strong immune system.
- Some people can have a severe illness from COVID-19, especially older adults and people with underlying medical conditions.
- If you have tested negative for the COVID-19 test, you should take steps to protect yourself and others by following the SOPs.

Prevention Tips

- Wash your hands with soap for 20 seconds. Use a hand sanitizer that contains at least 60% alcohol.
- Avoid close contact with others. Stay at least 6 feet from others.
- Wear a mask in public. The make cover will help protect others in case you are infected.
- Cover your coughs and sneezes with a tissue or the inside of your elbow. Throw used tissues in the trash and then wash your hands with soap and water for at least 20 seconds.